

ISic1515

I.Sicily inscription 1515

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stucco

Object

graffiti

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S. Giovanni

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἀνεπαύσατο
2. ἡ μείκρᾱ Νικοστράτη
3. τῆ πρὸ ιδ κα[λαν] [(δῶν)] Ἴουνίων
4. ἡμέρᾱ Ἑρμοῦ ὥραν δεκάτην
5. καὶ κατετέθη τῆ πρὸ ιβ καλ(ανδῶν) Ἴ[ο]υνί[ων]
6. ἡμέρᾱ Ἀφροδίτης

Apparatus

text of Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645015

Bibliography

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Cristiana*. 17: 43-81. At 51 no.4

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